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- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
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- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
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- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
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- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MODEL FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES BASED ON MOTIVATIONAL LEARNING APPROACH

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Abstract: Professional competencies have become one of the key determinants of career success in today's competitive and rapidly evolving labor market. Within higher education, these competencies encompass the knowledge, skills, abilities, and professional behaviors required for effective performance in professional settings. As higher education institutions increasingly seek to prepare students for the demands of contemporary workplaces, the motivational learning approach has emerged as an effective pedagogical strategy for developing professional competencies. By appropriately integrating intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors, educators can create learning environments that foster active student engagement, deeper learning, and the successful development of professional competencies. This article proposes a model for improving students' professional competencies based on a motivational learning approach that incorporates the principles of autonomy support, competence development, mastery-oriented goals, and collaborative learning. The proposed model consists of four interconnected phases—Preparation, Active Engagement, Reflection, and Integration—designed to promote the continuous development of competencies, provide systematic formative feedback, and facilitate the application of acquired competencies in authentic professional contexts. Ultimately, this approach encourages students to develop a growth mindset, strengthen their capacity for self-directed learning, and successfully transition from academic preparation to professional practice, thereby enhancing their readiness to meet the evolving demands of the modern labor market.

Key words: professional competencies, motivational learning, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, Self-Determination Theory (SDT), growth mindset, active learning, collaborative learning, autonomy.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi raqobatbardosh va dinamik mehnat bozorida kasbiy kompetensiyalar muvaffaqiyatli professional faoliyatning muhim omili hisoblanadi. Oliy ta'lim tizimida ushbu kompetensiyalar kasbiy faoliyatni samarali amalga oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma, malaka va kasbiy xulq-atvorni o'z ichiga oladi. Ta'lim tizimi talabalarni zamonaviy mehnat bozori va real kasbiy faoliyat talablariga tayyorlashga intilar ekan, motivatsion ta'lim yondashuvi kasbiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning samarali pedagogik vositasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ichki va tashqi motivatsiya omillaridan oqilona foydalanish orqali pedagoglar talabalarning o'quv jarayonidagi faolligini, chuqur o'zlashtirishini hamda kasbiy kompetensiyalarni muvaffaqiyatli shakllantirishini ta'minlaydigan ta'lim muhitini yaratishlari mumkin. Mazkur maqolada avtonomiyani qo'llab-quvvatlash, kompetensiyani rivojlantirish, o'zlashtirishga yo'naltirilgan maqsadlar (mastery goals) va hamkorlikdagi ta'lim tamoyillariga asoslangan motivatsion ta'lim yondashuvi orqali talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini takomillashtirish modeli taklif etiladi. Model o'zaro uzviy bog'langan to'rtta bosqichni – tayyorgarlik, faol ishtirok, refleksiya va integratsiya bosqichlarini qamrab olib, kompetensiyalarni izchil rivojlantirish, muntazam teskari aloqa (feedback)ni tashkil etish hamda ularni real kasbiy faoliyat sharoitlarida qo'llashni ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Natijada mazkur yondashuv talabalarda o'sishga yo'naltirilgan tafakkurni (growth mindset) shakllantirish, mustaqil ta'lim olish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish hamda akademik tayyorgarlikdan professional faoliyatga muvaffaqiyatli o'tishni ta'minlash orqali ularni zamonaviy mehnat bozori talablariga yanada puxta tayyorlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kasbiy kompetensiyalar, motivatsion ta'lim, ichki motivatsiya, tashqi motivatsiya, O'z-o'zini belgilash nazariyasi (Self-Determination Theory), o'sishga yo'naltirilgan tafakkur (growth mindset), faol ta'lim, hamkorlikdagi ta'lim, avtonomiya.

Аннотация: В современных условиях конкурентного и динамично развивающегося рынка труда профессиональные компетенции являются одним из ключевых факторов успешной профессиональной деятельности. В системе высшего образования они включают совокупность знаний, умений, навыков и моделей профессионального поведения, необходимых для эффективного выполнения профессиональных обязанностей. В условиях ориентации образовательных систем на подготовку студентов к реальным профессиональным вызовам мотивационный подход к обучению рассматривается как эффективное средство формирования и совершенствования профессиональных компетенций. Использование механизмов внутренней и внешней мотивации позволяет преподавателям создавать образовательную среду, способствующую более глубокому усвоению знаний, активному вовлечению студентов и успешному развитию ключевых профессиональных компетенций. В статье предлагается модель совершенствования профессиональных компетенций студентов на основе мотивационного образовательного подхода, включающего такие принципы, как поддержка автономии, развитие компетентности, ориентация на цели мастерства (mastery goals) и совместное обучение. Модель включает четыре взаимосвязанных этапа – подготовку, активное вовлечение, рефлекссию и интеграцию, обеспечивающих непрерывное развитие компетенций, организацию эффективной обратной связи и применение приобретённых компетенций в условиях реальной профессиональной деятельности. В конечном итоге предложенный подход способствует формированию у студентов установки на развитие (growth mindset), развитию навыков самостоятельного обучения и успешному переходу от академической подготовки к профессиональной деятельности, обеспечивая более высокий уровень готовности выпускников к требованиям современного рынка труда.

Ключевые слова: профессиональные компетенции, мотивационное обучение, внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация, теория самоопределения, установка на развитие (growth mindset), активное обучение, совместное обучение, автономия.

INTRODUCTION

Professional competencies constitute the foundation of success in today's competitive and dynamic labor market. Within the context of higher education, these competencies encompass the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and professional behaviors that enable students to perform effectively in their future careers. As higher education institutions increasingly focus on preparing graduates to meet the demands of real-world professional environments, identifying innovative approaches to competency development has become a priority. One promising approach is motivational learning, which utilizes motivational mechanisms to enhance students' engagement, learning outcomes, and professional competence development.

Motivation plays a decisive role in determining how students engage with learning activities, process information, and apply acquired knowledge in practice. By fostering both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, educators can create learning environments that encourage deeper engagement, sustained effort, and mastery of professional competencies. This article proposes a model for improving students' professional competencies through a motivational learning approach. Drawing upon contemporary motivational theories and empirical research, the proposed model offers a practical framework that can be implemented across diverse higher education settings to facilitate students' transition from academic learning to professional practice.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation occupies a central position in the educational process, influencing the amount of effort, persistence, and attention that students devote to learning activities ^[1; 9]. Among the most influential theoretical perspectives explaining academic motivation is Self-Determination Theory (SDT) developed by Deci and Ryan ^[8]. According to SDT, motivation exists on a continuum ranging from intrinsic motivation, in which individuals engage in activities because they find them inherently interesting and satisfying, to various forms of extrinsic motivation, where behavior is directed toward obtaining external rewards or avoiding negative consequences ^[2]. Intrinsic motivation is particularly valuable because it satisfies three fundamental psychological needs identified by SDT—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—which are essential for promoting sustained engagement, effective learning, and long-term professional development ^[3].

Within the process of professional competency development, motivation significantly influences students' willingness to participate actively in learning activities, seek additional learning opportunities, overcome challenges, and continuously improve their professional skills ^[4]. Highly motivated students demonstrate greater initiative, resilience, and responsibility throughout the learning process, which contributes substantially to the acquisition of both professional and transferable competencies. Consequently, motivational learning approaches emphasize creating educational environments that nurture intrinsic motivation while appropriately utilizing extrinsic motivational strategies when necessary ^[2]. Recent educational research also highlights that motivation should not be viewed as a stable learner characteristic but rather as a dynamic construct shaped

by instructional design, teacher support, learning experiences, and social interactions. Therefore, motivational learning environments should intentionally incorporate autonomy-supportive teaching, meaningful learning tasks, collaborative activities, and constructive feedback to facilitate sustainable professional competency development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Professional competencies encompass a broad spectrum of abilities required for successful professional performance. These include technical expertise, communication skills, teamwork, critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, adaptability, ethical decision-making, and lifelong learning skills. According to the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), professional competence also includes the ability to apply knowledge in practical situations, collaborate effectively with others, demonstrate responsibility, and exercise autonomy in professional contexts ^[9]. A major challenge facing higher education institutions is ensuring that students develop not only disciplinary knowledge but also the professional competencies required by modern employers. Achieving this objective requires instructional strategies that actively engage students, provide authentic learning experiences, and integrate real-world professional situations requiring analytical thinking, collaboration, and decision-making ^[6]. Traditional instructional methods, such as lecture-based teaching and textbook-centered learning, often fail to stimulate the level of engagement necessary for comprehensive competency development. In this regard, the motivational learning approach provides a more effective pedagogical alternative. The motivational learning approach integrates contemporary motivational theories with evidence-based instructional practices to strengthen both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

The proposed model is built upon six interrelated pedagogical principles: **Autonomy Support.** Providing students with meaningful choices throughout the learning process enhances their sense of ownership, responsibility, and self-determination, thereby strengthening intrinsic motivation. Opportunities for self-directed learning, individualized projects, and flexible learning pathways promote creativity, critical thinking, and independent professional development. **Mastery Goal Orientation.** Emphasizing mastery rather than performance encourages students to perceive learning as a process of continuous improvement rather than competition with others. Such an orientation promotes resilience, persistence, and deeper engagement with learning tasks, all of which contribute to the development of professional competencies. **Relevance.** Connecting theoretical knowledge with authentic professional practice increases students' perceived value of learning activities. The incorporation of case studies, internships, project-based learning, simulations, and real-world problem-solving enables students to recognize the practical significance of academic content for their future careers.

Feedback and Recognition. Continuous formative feedback focusing on progress, strategy use, and competency development enables students to recognize both their strengths and areas requiring further improvement ^[4]. Acknowledging students' achievements and developmental progress enhances motivation while encouraging continuous professional growth. **Social Learning.** Collaborative learning environments that encourage teamwork, peer discussion, project collaboration, and shared problem-solving strengthen students' motivation by fostering social connectedness and mutual support. Such environments also promote communication skills, leadership, and collaborative professional competencies. **Growth Mindset.** Encouraging students to adopt a growth mindset—the belief that intelligence and professional abilities can be continuously developed through effort, reflection, and learning—enhances resilience, persistence, and willingness to embrace challenging learning situations ^[5]. A growth mindset enables students to perceive mistakes as valuable learning opportunities rather than indicators of failure, thereby supporting long-term professional competency development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The proposed model for improving students' professional competencies integrates the principles of motivational learning into a comprehensive pedagogical framework. The model consists of four interconnected and cyclical phases: Preparation, Engagement, Reflection, and Integration. Together, these phases create a continuous process of competency development supported by ongoing feedback, self-regulation, and practical application. **Preparation Phase: Establishing Goals and Professional Expectations.** The first phase aims to create a motivational learning environment by clearly defining learning objectives and the professional competencies students are expected to develop. Students should understand the relevance of academic content to their future professional careers. This understanding can be strengthened through introductory seminars, discussions, presentations, and interactions with industry professionals who share authentic workplace experiences. Clearly defined and attainable learning goals provide students with a strong sense of purpose, direction, and responsibility throughout the educational process. During this phase, students are also encouraged to formu-

late individual learning goals based on their personal interests and professional aspirations. Such self-directed learning strengthens intrinsic motivation by satisfying learners' need for autonomy. Furthermore, students receive instruction in essential self-regulation skills, including goal setting, time management, self-monitoring, and reflective planning, all of which constitute fundamental professional competencies. Engagement Phase: Active and Collaborative Learning.

The engagement phase focuses on sustaining students' motivation and active participation in the learning process. Instruction is organized around active learning strategies that promote critical thinking, problem-solving, decision-making, and practical application of knowledge. Students participate in authentic learning activities such as simulations, case studies, project-based assignments, field practice, and internships, enabling them to transfer theoretical knowledge into professional contexts. Collaborative learning represents another essential component of this phase. Group projects, peer interaction, and collaborative problem-solving activities enable students to strengthen communication, teamwork, leadership, and conflict-resolution skills, all of which are essential professional competencies. Such collaborative environments also promote knowledge sharing, mutual support, and social responsibility. The instructional process emphasizes mastery-oriented learning rather than performance-oriented competition. Consequently, assessment focuses primarily on students' competency development, learning strategies, and continuous improvement instead of solely evaluating final outcomes or examination scores. This approach encourages deeper cognitive engagement and long-term professional growth. Reflection Phase: Feedback and Self-Regulated Learning. Reflection constitutes a critical stage in consolidating newly acquired competencies and promoting continuous improvement. During this phase, students engage in self-assessment, peer assessment, and instructor feedback designed to evaluate both learning processes and competency development.

Reflective practices—including learning journals, portfolio analysis, structured discussions, and individual consultations—enable students to identify their strengths, recognize areas requiring improvement, and establish new developmental goals. Constructive feedback should be timely, specific, actionable, and focused on improvement rather than personal judgment. Such feedback enhances learners' self-efficacy and encourages them to perceive mistakes as opportunities for professional growth. The reflection phase also strengthens students' metacognitive awareness by encouraging them to evaluate the effectiveness of their learning strategies, monitor their progress, and regulate subsequent learning activities independently. Integration Phase: Applying Competencies in Professional Contexts The final phase emphasizes transferring acquired competencies to authentic professional environments [10]. Students apply their knowledge and skills through internships, service-learning projects, professional simulations, industry partnerships, and workplace-based learning experiences.

These authentic learning opportunities facilitate the transition from academic preparation to professional practice while reinforcing the practical value of higher education. Successful application of competencies in real-world situations increases students' confidence, professional identity, and intrinsic motivation for lifelong learning and continuous self-development [11]. Moreover, this phase provides valuable feedback for higher education institutions by demonstrating the extent to which graduates are capable of transferring academic knowledge into effective professional performance. The findings obtained during this stage may subsequently inform curriculum revision, instructional improvement, and competency-based assessment practices.

CONCLUSION

The proposed motivational learning model demonstrates that the development of professional competencies depends not only on curriculum content but also on the quality of students' motivation and engagement throughout the educational process. By integrating autonomy support, mastery-oriented learning, relevance of educational content, constructive feedback, collaborative learning, and growth mindset principles, the model creates conditions that facilitate sustained motivation, critical thinking, professional responsibility, and lifelong learning.

Unlike traditional instructional approaches that primarily emphasize knowledge acquisition, the proposed model encourages students to become active participants in their own professional development. Through its four interconnected phases—Preparation, Engagement, Reflection, and Integration—the model establishes a continuous cycle of competency development supported by self-regulation, reflective practice, and authentic professional experience. The implementation of this model within higher education institutions has the potential to strengthen curriculum quality, improve competency-based instruction, and better prepare graduates for the rapidly changing demands of the twenty-first-century labor market. Future empirical research should validate the effectiveness of the proposed model through experimental and longitudinal studies involving diverse student populations and professional disciplines.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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